

Loan Repayment Status of Small Holder Farmers of Oromia Credit and Saving Share Company Clients: The Case From Adola Rede Woreda Guji Zone, Oromia, Ethiopia

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Abstract – The major concern of this study is to assess the loan repayment status of small holder farmers of the OCSSCo clients. Based on the ground evidence of survey data results, small holder households of AdolaRede cannot able to implement improved agricultural activities with their own funds. They need credit from lending institutions to implement their agriculture and other livelihood activities. The main problem of farmers of the localities is the shortage of capital. The credit institution wouldn't borrow money unless the credit taken by households is repaid. For the purpose of this study, primary data were collected from small holder farmers selected purposively in consultation with Oromia Credit and saving share company office of the district. A total of 154 households of OCSSCo clients were included in the final analysis. In addition, secondary data were collected from the district of OCSSCo, Journals, research findings and different reports. Descriptive statistics such as mean, tables, standard deviation and percentages were used for analyzing the data. To identify loan repayment status, two limit Tobit model was employed. In this regard, a total of fourteen explanatory variables were included in the empirical model of which five were significant. VIF and multicollinearity test and Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test to detect Heteroscedasticity problem were employed. Distance from the main market, family size, credit amount, off-farm activities and cooperative membership were important in influencing the loan repayment status of small holders, either positively or negatively as evidenced by the model output.

Keywords: Credit, small holders, loan repayment, Micro Finance.

1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Ethiopia is among least developed countries by having wealthy heritage and culture, bordered by Kenya, south Sudan, Djibouti, Eritrea and Somalia (FAO, 2011). Agriculture is the back bone of the country's economy which accounts for 42% NGDP. Industry contributes to 12% and services 46% of GDP (FAO, 2011). This shows a less agricultural efficiency. Low agricultural efficiency areas are featured by constant rural poverty, as well as population density always leads to vicious circle of poverty and environmental degradation (Awulachew et al., 2011). In Ethiopia, the role that agricultural development plays in economic development is very monumental and it meets the very important needs of human being as well as small scale irrigation (Seleshi, 2010). Ethiopia has the history of relying on rain-fed agriculture to meet their needs and as a result of this strategy, the people of the country has faced many challenges over the years; these challenges are; short fall of food arising from disasters (MoFED, 2008). In other ways, Ethiopia has recorded fast economic growth over the past decade, with an average growth rate of 10.7% per year for the period ranging from 2003/04 to

2011/12MoA (2015). Growth reflected a mix of factors, including agricultural modernization, development of new export sectors, strong global commodity demand and government-led development investments. The government of Ethiopia is currently implementing the Growth and Transformation Plan (GTP) which sets a long-term goal of becoming a middle-income country by 2025. Agriculture remained a dominant sector and an important source of economic growth. Over the past 15 years, the average agricultural growth rate has been close to 7% per annum (ibid). For undertaking agricultural activities credit sectors plays a significant role, Banks and MFIs have been delivering their service since long time ago. For instance, Tsehay and Mengistu, (2002) (cited in Kebede, et al., 2002) indicated that delivery of financial service can be through saving and service has been delivered by an official and official financial market. For example, local micro finance institutions were one official financial institutions targeting the poor rural and urban community in the country following the insurance proclamation No 40/96 which regulates the business of microfinance in the country. Depending on a various un official loan like village money lenders, colleagues and traders. But, since the process is expensive and un realistic it is not advisable. This activities are take place mainly due to un appropriate procedures of financial institutions for the poor local communities. The ability to get access to formal financial credit from financial institutions enable local poor farmers to improve their wealth, productivity and health conditions (Bauchet et al., 2011).

1.1 Research Questions

- How do you consider significance of credit loan of small holder farmers of oromia credit and saving share company?
- What are the factors affecting formal sources of credit loan repayment status of OCSSC Clients?
- What is the use status of credit for smallholder farmers in the district?

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- To Describe purpose of credit loan among smallholder farmers in the study area;
- To examine factors affecting formal source of credit loan repayment status of OCSSCo Clients and
- To evaluate the use status of credit for low income community in the woreda

1.3 Purpose of the Research

The current research was conducted on re payment of loan status of the poor community of OCSSCo Clients is a vital tool for both the OCSSCo and the smallholder farmers of OCSSCo clients. These is the fact due to that, the major livelihood activities of Adola Rede district smallholder farmers is based on agriculture and the major problem of small holder farmers of the localities is the limitation of financial capital to access the inputs of agriculture. Therefore, studies on the assessment of loan repayment status of Smallholder farmers of OCSSCo clients are vital to enable governmental and non-governmental financial institutions, policy makers, policy implementers, as well as borrowers to have knowledge as to where and how to channel efforts in order to minimize loan defaults and help to design successful credit programs in the study area and outside of it. It also serves as a reference material for researchers.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The study was focus on assessing loan repayment status of smallholder farmers' of OCSSCo clients of Adola Rede Woreda. The area coverage of the study was limited to 6 kebeles found in the district. The study was

estimate the extent to which the households are repaying loans and identify factors influencing households credit repaying status and the use status of the credit with cross sectional data that will be collected at specific year of 2017/18 productions and loan repaying years.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Emergency of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs)

For many years, formal financial institutions have not served the poor farmers properly. In the least developing countries, the poor section of the community did not get access to financial institutions. They were simply kept out of the rich for a long period of time. Because, the financial institutions require collateral, they prefer high income customers with large loan, the process and procedures in the institutions are very long and complex bureaucratic system and most of the time the financial institutions are urban based. (Bournan, 1984, cited in Padma and Getachew, 2005; Chowdhury (N.D; Gbate, 1992); Khapdker, 1998; and Henk M, 1998).

2.2 Ethiopian Financial Institutions

Least developed countries specifically Africa's financial markets are mainly not developed well due to lack of effective financial systems. specially, loan, deposit as well as insurance markets in the country side are mainly under developed (Morduch, 1995). Financial markets in Ethiopia includes: Commercial CBE, AIDB, MFIs, Cooperatives bank as well as others private banks are participating in the sector of financial markets activities (Jemaneh, 2002). Due to more liquidity these institutions are highly criticized by poor farmers However, key reforms has been taken since in 1991. Due to these critical reforms, currently the system that mainly encourage the low income farmers is established and its performance is in progress.

2.3 Research Gaps

As the researcher concluded from the literature reviewed, issue gaps and contextual (geographical) gaps which need to be addressed in the current study

Fig -1: Conceptual Framework of the study
Source: Drown by the researcher(2023)

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sampling Procedure

To select sampling respondents, three stages sampling technique were used. In the first stage, out of 31 kebeles found in the district, credit taker kebeles were selected purposively in consultation with Oromia Credit and Saving Share Company office of the district. Secondly, six Kebeles are chosen by simple random technique. In the third stage, given the available resource and time at the disposal of the researcher, from list of smallholder farmer of OCSSC client's households in the sample kebeles, a total of 154 sample loan takers were selected randomly using probability proportional to sample size (pps). By considering the level of precision that were tolerated and confidence level, sample size is determined for the study. Sampling error committed for this study is 8% with confidence interval of 92%. The sample size is determined by using Yamane (1967:886) formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (0.0064)$$

So by using the above formula the sample size for the study were determined from the study population 8807 households, study sample for this research were

$$n = \frac{8807}{1+8807(0.08)^2} = 8807/57.3684 = \sim 154$$

This selected household was distributed for the six purposively selected kebeles by using proportional allocation techniques. The sample size of the study population were taken as constant are multiplied by total household in respective kebeles to allocate sample to it.

$$nk = Nk \left(\frac{n}{N} \right)$$

Where:-nk = sample size for kebele k

Nk= total household in kebele k

K = 1,2,3,4,5,6 [Anferara, Dole, Derartu, Kiltusorsa, Billu& Dande]

n = total sample size (n=n1+n2+n3+n4+n5+n6)

N = total household in six kebeles.

3.2 Methods of Data Analysis

For this particular study, in the data analysis parts, both descriptive and econometrics tools were used. In this case, the researcher used the Tobit model for analysis.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Problems Hindering Farmers Saving and Investment Decisions

The analysed result shows that, the major problems affecting farmers saving and investment decisions was lack of capital to buy agricultural inputs that accounts 44.80 percent, limited marketing opportunity 27.27

percent, low price of agricultural products 26.62 percent and other reasons that account 1.29 percent (Table 1).

Table -1: Problems affecting farmers saving and investment activities

S. N	Problems	Percentage
1	Low price of agricultural products	26.62
2	Limited marketing opportunity	27.27
3	Lack of Capitals to buy agricultural inputs	44.80
4	Others	1.29

Source: Computed from own survey, (2023)

4.2.1 Diagnostic Tests

Two common tests were conducted on the regression model. These diagnostic tests are multicollinearity (which tests for presence of high correlation among explanatory variables) and Heteroscedasticity (which tests whether error terms have constant variance). According to Reddy et al., (2013), correlation among independent variables or a problem of multicollinearity is mostly occurred difficulty econometrics data results. The source of the problem could be due to selection of the indicators or items having high correlation between one another as well as it resulted in low forecasting errors. In this study, in order to check the existence of multicollinearity is a problem with the data at hand or not, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was used for detection of multicollinearity. Generally, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) indicates how the variance of an estimator is inflated due to the presence of multicollinearity. The problem of multicollinearity is severe as VIF approaches infinity and in the absence of multicollinearity, VIF will be equal to 1. Variance Inflation Factor for each explanatory variable (X_i) can be calculated as stated in Gujarati (2004)

According to the data at hand, multicollinearity test result shows that the mean VIF of all explanatory variables included in the model was 1.58 indicating that there was no serious problem of multicollinearity (Appendix 1). Heteroskedasticity is also another estimation problem which results in inefficient estimation if the problem is not resolved.

Table -2: Multicollinearity Test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
Age of households	3.37	0.296595
Family size of households	2.90	0.345135
Loan experience	1.75	0.571323
Education level of households	1.60	0.625078
Log of credit amount	1.43	0.698966
Sex of households	1.35	0.738468

Land holding size	1.30	0.766309
Number of oxen owned	1.30	0.766348
Festival spending	1.25	0.797610
Distance to extension service center	1.24	0.807557
Lagged product price perception	1.22	0.819411
Off-farm participation	1.17	0.851083
Distance to main market	1.16	0.863252
Cooperative membership	1.10	0.907606
Mean	1.58	

Source: statistical analysis(2023)

4.2.2 Factor Affecting Intensity of Loan Repayment

The estimation results of two-limit to bit regression model is indicated in Table7. Regression results showed that the model was statistically significant at 1% significance level indicating the goodness of fit of the model to explain the relationships of the hypothesized variables or acceptance of alternative hypothesis that states at least one covariate is related to the dependent variable. Also, the model output indicates that out of the total of fourteen independent variables hypothesized to affect intensity of loan repayment, five variables were found to significantly affect the intensity of loan repayment at various significance levels. Intensity of loan repayment in the study area was influenced by family size of households, membership in cooperatives, off-farm participation, distance to main market, and amount of credit received. The Pseudo R2 was 0.1113, indicating the variables included in the model explain 11.13% of the variation in the intensity of loan repaid. In the study area, households’ expected intensity of loan repaid was 55.05% for average households. An average household had an 88.05% predicted probabilities of being non-defaulters.

Table -3: Factors affecting intensity of loan repayment

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Marginal Effect
Sex of household heads	-0.124	0.144	-0.020
Age of household heads	-0.001	0.013	-0.001
Education level of household heads	-0.007	0.023	-0.001
Family size	0.054**	0.023	0.008
Membership in cooperatives	0.201*	0.112	0.032
Off-farm participation	-0.300**	0.137	-0.048

Lagged product price perception	0.091	0.177	0.014
Land holding size	0.010	0.079	0.001
Number of oxen owned	-0.027	0.031	-0.004
Festival spending	-0.003	0.019	-0.000
Loan experience	-0.012	0.063	-0.002
Distance to extension service center	0.002	0.003	0.001
Distance to main market	-0.030***	0.011	-0.005
Log of credit amount	-0.154**	0.073	-0.025
Constant	2.461	0.885	
Sigma	0.687	0.069	

Source: statistical analysis(2023)

Family size of household heads was among the factors affecting intensity of market loan repayment positively and significantly at 5% significance level. A unit addition in family size of households increases intensity of loan repayment by 0.008. This relationship is as expected, since larger family size could have larger family labors which contribute to agricultural production thereby increase their income and loan repayment capacity. Membership in cooperatives had a significant and positive influence on intensity of loan repayment at 10% significance level. This means, intensity of loan repayment is higher for members of cooperatives as compared to non-members. Alternatively, being a member in cooperatives increases intensity of loan repayment. This could be due to the fact that membership in cooperatives by farmers allows them to have better prices for their output which could in turn increase their income and their repayment capacity. A marginal effect implies that, as compared to non-members, intensity of loan repayment for members' increases by 0.032. Off-farm participation has negative and significant effect on intensity of loan repayment at 5% significance level and income from agricultural production which is dominant income source for the farming households which could in turn reduce their loan repayment capacity and making them loan defaulters. Marginal effect implies that, as compared to off-farm non-participant, intensity of loan repayment for off-farm participant decreases by 0.048. Distance to the main market was also hypothesized to affect intensity of loan repayment in the study area. As hypothesized it has negative and significant effect on intensity of loan repayment at 1% significance level. As the households a kilometer farther away from the main market, their intensity of loan repayment decreases by 0.005. Negative association between intensity of loan repayment and distance to main market is due to the fact that the farther the residences of the household from the main market, the lesser farmers' awareness about price information, the higher cost of transportation that will decrease their income base and their loan repayment capacity. Amount credit received was also among factors affecting intensity of loan repayment. It has significant effect on intensity of loan repayment at 5% significance level. Marginal effect of this variable would signify a 1% increase in amount of credit received by household will decrease intensity of loan repayment by 0.025. This is because, with larger size of credit received, households income and loan repayment capacity decreases as households

agricultural investment and earning is highly influenced by climate and marketing shocks that decrease size of output harvested and marketed due to production failure.

5. CONCLUSION

In developing countries, nowadays, the prevalence of poverty has become a critical challenge. Absence of effective financial institutions are among the problems which increase poor farmers in local community. Due to this, the present study is aimed to assess the loan repayment status of OCSSCo clients of Adola Rede districts of Guji Zone. For this particular study a total sample of 154 rural smallholder farmers that obtained loan from Oromia Credit and Saving Share Company of Adola Rede district were used. To analyze the sample data collected from smallholders, descriptive statistics and a two limit Tobit model were employed. In this study, results of descriptive statistics shows, 42.2 (%) were non-defaulters and the remaining 57.79(%) were defaulters. Among the defaulters, 14.28 (%) were complete defaulters, while 43.50 (%) repaid some amount of the total loan which they borrowed. Of the total sample household heads, 60.4 percent were male household heads and the remaining 39.6% were female household heads. Among the borrowers, 27.27 percent of the defaulter and 41.66 percent of non-defaulters were female headed households respectively. The average birr borrowed by households from Oromia credit and saving Share Company was 37,059 birr with minimum of 3,000 birr and maximum 200,000 birr. The mean expected amount of credit to be repaid was 41,386.35 birr with minimum and maximum of 3,510 and 220,000 birr respectively. Among this, the proportion of credit repaid was 62.8% that deviated from defaulters to non-defaulters. Regarding to the activities that the households participated in with a credit loan they borrowed, 37.01 percent uses credit for cattle fattening, 24.67 percents for trade, 20.12 percent for services (buying motor, etc) and 18.18 percent for crop production. The estimation result shows that family size affects loan repayment positively, that is the larger family could have larger family labor which contribute to agricultural production thereby increase their income and loan repayment capacity. Membership in cooperatives has also significant and positive influence on intensity of loan repayment. This means, intensity of loan repayment is higher for members of cooperatives as compared to non-members. In this study, off-farm participation has a significant effect on intensity of loan repayment and income from agricultural production which is dominant income source for the farming households which could in turn reduce their loan repayment capacity and making them loan defaulters. In the study, case of the distance from main markets, as the households a kilometer farther away from the main market, their intensity of loan repayment decreases by 0.005. Amount of credit has negative effects on loan repayment status of the study, as the households borrowed a high amount of credit produce more and climate changes affect their products. To test the adequacy of the model, two common diagnostic tests were conducted. These are diagnostic tests for presence of severe correlation among explanatory variables (Multicollinearity) and distribution of error term (Heteroscedasticity). To detect whether the multicollinearity is a problem with the data at hand or not, Variance Inflating Factor (VIF) was used for detection of multicollinearity. In this study, test result shows that, the mean VIF of all explanatory variables included in the model was 1.58 indicating that there was no serious problem of multicollinearity. Heteroskescedasticity is also another estimation problem which results in inefficient estimation if the problem is not resolved.

5.1 Theoretical Implication

The current research was conducted on the loan repayment status of the smallholder farmers of the OCSSCo Clients is a vital tool for both the OCSSCo and the smallholder farmers of OCSSCo clients. These is the fact due to that, the major livelihood activities of Adola Rede district smallholder farmers is based on agriculture and

the major problem of small holder farmers of the localities is the limitation of financial capital to access the inputs of agriculture. Therefore, studies on the assessment of loan repayment status of Smallholder farmers of OCSSCo clients are vital to enable governmental and non-governmental financial institutions, policy makers, policy implementers, as well as borrowers to have knowledge as to where and how to channel efforts in order to minimize loan defaults and help to design successful credit programs in the study area and outside of it. It also serves as a reference material other researchers.

5.2 Recommendation

This research provides a basis for undertaking similar studies in similar environments. The finding shows that, Oromia Credit and Saving Share Company should provide the service in near-by kebeles, because smallholder farmers face transportation difficulties when travelling long distances to obtain the service. To satisfy a large number of clients and collecting the loan on time, to minimize defaulting rate, OCSSCo increase its capacity in terms of capital and manpower. To minimize default rate, OCSSCo officers should be able to giving advice before lending; how and what to do, management of agricultural products outputs and capital. The government should facilitate the road and markets near the living area of the smallholder farmers where they sold their products. In farmers' side, the smallholders should participate in activities that the credit is planned for, rather than becoming busy in participating in unplanned activities that lead them to default. In addition, the researcher recommends farmers to produce products that resist a harsh climate conditions and/or use diversification. To plough their farmland as well as sold in unexpected situation of bad times, the farmers should own oxen as much as possible.

5.3 Suggestions for future research

Since this study was mainly focused on quantitative method, farther qualitative technique will important to get farther result on loan re payment status of small holder farmers of OCSSCo. Farther more, the study focus on only OCSSCo. Therefore, other researchers should conduct similar studies on other financial institutions

5.4 Authors' Contribution

I hereby we declare that, this study was our original work and that all materials used for this study has been acknowledged well.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ably, Z., Alemayehu, W., Daneil, T. & Yelma, G., 2000. Introduction to research methods, graduate studies and research office. AAU.
- [2] Ajay, S. & Micahmasuku, B., 2014. Sampling Techniques & Determination of Sample Size in Applied Statistics Research an overview. International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, Vol. II (Issue 11).
- [3] Ali, D.A. & Deininger, K., 2012. Causes and implications of credit rationing in rural Ethiopia: The importance of spatial variation. In Policy Research Working Paper. Washington DC: World Bank. p.No. 6096.
- [4] Amha, W., 2011. Meeting the Financial Needs of Smallholder Farmers in Ethiopia: In African Smallholders Food Crops, Markets and Policy.
- [5] Anon., 2008. Dynamics of Growth and Poverty in Ethiopia (1995/96–2004/05). Ministry of Finance and Economic Development.

- [6] Anon., 2011. Independent evaluation of the program and cooperation of the food and agriculture organization of the united nations in Ethiopia. FAO.
- [7] Anon., 2015. Agricultural Growth Program II (AGP-II) Program design document. Addis Ababa: Ministry of agriculture.
- [8] Anon., 2015. Socio-economic profile of each district categorized with their respective zone's until 2008. Bureau of Finance and Economic Development.
- [9] Anon., 2015. State of food security 2015 Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Rome. FAO.
- [10] Awulachew, Seleshi & Mekonin, A., n.d. Performance of Irrigation: An Assessment. *Journal Of Experimental Agriculture*, 47(1), pp.57-69.
- [11] Bashir, m., K., Mehmood, Y. & Hassan, S., 2010. Impact of agricultural credit on Productivity of wheat crop: Evidence from Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. *Pak. J. Agri. Sci*, 47, pp.405-09.
- [12] Coles, J.L., Daniel, N.D. & Naveen, L., n.d. Managerial incentives and risk taking *Journal of Financial Economics. Sci*, 47, pp.431-68.
- [13] Dercon, S., Gilligan, D.O., Hoddinott, J. & Woldehanna, T., 2009. The impact of agricultural extension and roads on poverty and consumption Growth in fifteen Ethiopian villages.. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 91, pp.1007-21.
- [14] Dong, F., Lu, J. & Featherstone, A.M., 2010. Effects of Credit Constraints on Productivity and Rural Household Income in China, Working Paper. Center for Agricultural and Rural Development, Iowa State University, USA, 10 -WP 516.
- [15] Ethiopia Population, 2018. [Online] Available at: HYPERLINK "http://worldometers.info/Ethiopia_population2018" http://worldometers.info/Ethiopia_population2018.
- [16] Gebrehiwot, A., 2002. Microfinance Institutions in Ethiopia: Issues of Portfolio Risk.
- [17] Girma, K., 2011. The contribution of small scale irrigation to households' income and food security: the case of Gembelater irrigation scheme, east wellega zone of oromia. Addis Ababa.
- [18] Greene, W.H., 2000. *Econometric Analysis*. Fourth ed. Inc, New York: pretice Hall International.
- [19] Johnston, J. & J Dinardo, 1997. *Econometrics Methods*. 4th ed. Inc, New York: The mcgraw-Hill Companies.
- [20] Karlan, D.S., 2001. Microfinance impact assessments: the perils of using new Members as a control group. *Journal of Microfinance/ESR Review*, 3, pp.75-85.
- [21] Kassa, Y., 2010. Regulation and Supervision of Microfinance Business in Ethiopia: Achievements, Challenges & Prospects, National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE). Addis Ababa.
- [22] Lynne, G., D., S. Shonkwilere, J. & L., R.R., 1988. Attitudes and Farmer Conservation Behavior. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 70, pp.12-19.
- [23] Mcsweeney & B., G., 1979. collection and Analysis of Data on Rural Women's Time Use Studies in Family Planning. 10(11/12), pp.379 - 383.
- [24] MPUGA, P., 2010. Constraints in access to and demand for rural credit: Evidence from Uganda. *African Development Review*, 22, pp.115-48.